

PRINCIPLE OF PUBLICITY AND VOLUNTARY EVENTS IN CULTURAL EVENTS.

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Annotation: This article provides information on the organization of cultural events, the main functions of cultural and educational institutions, the promotion and promotion of cultural events, the development of folk art, the organization of public recreation.

Key words: forms of cultural events, group forms, mass forms, monologic forms, dialogic forms, complex forms, principle, principle of mass and voluntariness, function.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, in May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

The work forms of cultural and educational activities are diverse and numerous. In order to have a complete and systematic understanding of them, a special classification is necessary. There are several types of classification in special literature: Among them, two types of classification are more noteworthy: the first type of classification is based on the number of people participating in cultural and educational forms of work. It is divided into: individual, group and mass forms.

Individual forms consist of consultation between a specialist and a listener, individual (one-on-one) conversation, and practical training.

Group forms - events with the participation of approximately 15-30 people, i.e. include discussions, seminars, talks, excursions, artistic amateur collectives.

Public forms - unlimited number of lectures for a large audience, question-and-answer evenings, oral journals, thematic evenings, public performances, holidays, etc. Mass forms are the main part of cultural and educational work.

The second type of classification is based on the use of effective tools and methods in the forms of cultural and educational work. This type of classification is mostly related to propaganda and propaganda work in cultural and educational institutions. In this regard, work forms are divided into three: monologic, dialogic, and complex forms. Monological forms are actions that convey information to the audience through the oral, “live” words of the speaker and other effective means. For example: lecture, information, etc.

Dialogic forms are activities that mainly consist of dialogue, discussion, and exchange of ideas, including conversations, discussions, meetings, and question-and-answer evenings. Complex forms mean activities in which many other effective means can be used in addition to the use of monologic and dialogic speeches. For example: an oral journal, thematic evening, public cultural events, etc.

Common forms in current cultural and educational work are mass forms of the first classification and complex forms of the second.

The concept of artistic and public events helps to better reveal the nature of both public and complex forms of work in cultural and educational institutions. It should be noted that artistic and public events are still called “cultural-public events”, “public events”, “public forms” in practice. Mass cultural events are a type of cultural event directed to the consumer of a specific social reality, information in a figurative way. Cultural events are based on:

- Carrying out campaigning and promotion work.
- Cultivation of folk art.
- Organization of public recreation.

Mass-cultural events help people in their spare time to provide them with the necessary information, to provide them with artistic and aesthetic pleasure, to attract them to cultural and creative work, and to have meaningful leisure.

The most advantageous aspect of public cultural events is that they embody the activities of cultural and educational institutions. In particular, activities such as promotion and propaganda work, amateur creativity, meaningful organization of free time are combined in them. If we refer to every form of mass-cultural events (public holidays, traditional ceremonies, theatrical performances, various parties, demonstrations), they are created for the promotion and propaganda content, the results of amateur creativity, artistic-aesthetic pleasure and entertainment. comforts are evident. Therefore, the public-cultural event is a generalized reflection of all activities in cultural-educational institutions.

While learning the theory of cultural events, it is important to know their essence and place in social and cultural life, it is also important to study their unique principles and functions (tasks) on a scientific basis.

The specific principles of mass-cultural events are the main source of guidance in their organization. Principle is “the basic rule of theory, teaching, science and the like”, “law and regulation that is used as a basis for activity”. A principle is a rule that must be followed. Since public cultural events are a part of ideological work, cultural and educational activities, they are primarily subject to general ideological principles. These include:

- The principle of idealism and nationalism.
- Scientific principle.
- The principle of connection with life, social practice.
- The principle of ideological struggle.
- The principle of differential approach to different groups and classes of the population.

These universal ideological principles play the role of the main charter in the activities of social institutions that carry out all ideological work, including the organization of cultural events.

At the same time, there are specific principles of cultural and educational activities, including cultural events. They are created on the basis of the essence of cultural and educational works,

the role they play in life. In turn, these specific principles create the main tasks of cultural and educational work and the rules of organization of all forms of work.

The specific principles of cultural and educational work, including artistic and public events, are as follows: The principle of publicity and voluntariness. It is optional to come to events organized in cultural and educational institutions. No one can be forced to participate in events. Residents can choose events they like and participate in them. Events must be popular and interesting for everyone. To achieve this, the organized activities should be of a high level and meet the basic spiritual needs and requirements of the population. Poetic works created by representatives of classical literature are highly valued by our people as examples of high creativity.[4]

The principle of initiative and amateurism of the public. Events are organized exclusively for and with the participation of local residents. In professional groups, performances are prepared by professional performers - actors, soloists, dancers, and in cultural and educational institutions, the participants and members of events are mainly public initiators and amateurs. That's why it is necessary to widely involve initiative people and members of artistic amateur groups in organizing the event and use their activities effectively.

The principle of enriching and growing the spiritual image of a person. It is known that a person cannot fully satisfy his needs during the main work process and outside of it. In this regard, cultural and educational institutions, including various events held in them, can help. For this purpose, it is necessary to find out what activities the population does in their spare time, what areas they are interested in and what they need, and organize special events based on certain requirements.

The principle of combining information and art (informational logic and emotional imagery). At cultural events, information and knowledge are given to the public to a certain extent. They should be understandable, artistically perfect and impressive in order to interest the population more. For this purpose, it is necessary to convey the information to the public in a more artistic and emotional image form, with extensive use of effective means.

The principle of beautifying the content of the recreation process. Events are mainly organized during the free time of the main work of the population and special forms of recreation are referred to them. In order for residents to have a good time, events should be organized based on aesthetic enrichment and beauty laws. Beautiful, beautiful, artistic-aesthetic decoration of the place of the event, the form of the organized event, its content, actions and words will have a great effect.

Creative assimilation of the specific principles of general ideological and cultural-educational works mentioned above serves as the main scientific weapon for the organizers of cultural events. The main functions of cultural events are based on their general and specific principles. Function means the duties performed by any institution, person or thing within the scope of activity. Just as every institution has its own scope of work, cultural and educational institutions also have their own activities and tasks. Since cultural events are one of the main areas of cultural and educational institutions, first of all, their functions should be performed with a creative approach in their own way.

Cultural and educational institutions perform the following main functions (tasks) in their work: Providing continuous education to the public, continuous and regular improvement of

their knowledge. Attracting the public to amateur creativity, increasing their cultural and social activity and initiative. Meaningful organization of residents' recreation.

These functions are common to all activities and fields of cultural and educational institutions. But in each of his activities, these functions are used in a unique way. In some activities, for example, in the activities of the public university, the first function is in the organization of lectures, oral agitation and propaganda work, in other activities (for example, in the development of amateur creativity), the second function, in some others, including the organization of art and public events, the third function is important. This function is used in artistic and public events, based on its essence, in a specific order. They are as follows: Organization of public recreation. It is known that people often come to cultural events tired after work. For this reason, all events should serve as meaningful recreation for them. If all events create conditions for public recreation and artistic-aesthetic pleasure, then it can be said that the work has been done according to the purpose. The art of cinema is an important tool in shaping the audience's perception, vision and aesthetic taste of reality.[5]

Other functions of cultural and educational institutions, i.e. providing knowledge to the public and organizing amateur creativity, are carried out directly in relation to public recreation. Providing information and knowledge to the public. This unique function is a modified form of the first function specific to the activities of cultural and educational institutions, adapted to public events. Continuous systematic education and imparting knowledge in cultural events is a complex process. The process of continuous education can be carried out by the means of oral agitation and propaganda, including lectures, thematic readings. This task can be performed by one of the forms of art-public events - oral magazines, and all other cultural-public events can provide information and knowledge specific to the topic. The most important requirement of the process of providing information and knowledge in cultural events is that it is necessary to avoid familiar knowledge and use new and original information. In order to use such information, it is good to refer to special information, encyclopedias and archival materials related to activities, and prepare an event based on them. Attracting the public to artistic amateur creativity. Of course, cultural events do not exist without amateur creativity. The activity of all people participating in the preparation of the event is, without a word, a form of artistic creativity. But when we say "Involvement of the public in amateur creativity", we should understand not only the activities of the organizers of the event, but also the activation of the public who came as spectators, turning them into participants of the general action. In many forms of artistic and public work, especially in holidays and folk traditions, there are ample facilities for this process. In the process of preparing cultural events, it is important to refer to the specific organizational features of a certain form of work in the performance of the above-mentioned function. Because these functions are not used equally when organizing different forms of work. In some forms, more information is provided, some serve mainly for recreation, and others help to participate in a more cultural and creative process. A. Lunacharsky highly evaluated the role of artistic promotion and propaganda in influencing the public and emphasized several times that it is necessary to enrich propaganda and propaganda with artistic means and to give propaganda character to art forms. Another important feature of public art events is to make the public a participant in the event. The advantage of calling events organized in cultural and educational institutions public is that they are organized for the public

and take place with the participation of the public. If in theater, cinema and television there is an invisible "wall" between the participants of the work and the audience, and the public plays only the role of the audience, then the active participation of the public is envisaged in artistic and public events. Since a certain event is a certain moment in the life of the local population, the public participates in it as people who express their opinion and attitude to a certain event. Of course, it is difficult to actively participate in the event. Its main participants are members of pre-determined artistic amateur collectives and speakers. But the organizer of the event should not be satisfied with these main participants, but should also use ways to activate the public and turn them into participants of the event. Art captures a person more than anyone when he becomes an audience or a listener, but when he actively participates in a public movement, N. K. Krupskaya said. This process is a characteristic feature of artistic and public events, it connects the people who create social life to the creative process and increases their social and cultural activity.

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